

INTERPRETATIONS OF SEMANTIC DERIVATION (IN THE CASE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

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Annotation: The article is in modern linguistics and more and more new aspects of derivation are being discovered, it is divided into lexical, syntactic, semantic, morphological, formal. It is being launched into types, and derivational relations through English-Uzbek languages are discussed.

Keywords: linguocognitology, distributive analysis, derivation, linguistic models, speech linguistics, text derivation.

Аннотация: В статье в современном языкознании открываются все новые и новые аспекты словообразования, оно делится на лексическое, синтаксическое, семантическое, морфологическое, формальное, запускается на типы, обсуждаются словообразовательные отношения через англо-узбекские языки.

Ключевые слова: лингвокогнитология, дистрибутивный анализ, деривация, лингвистические модели, лингвистика речи, деривация текста.

In modern linguistics newer and newer derivation aspects are unfolding, it is lexical, syntactic, semantic, morphological, and formal an attempt is being made to divide into species.

Historical roots of derivatively the use of language is always new to the time of Descartes, who believed that stems, according to his opinion, from the language with nothing to use there is no way to limit it. Simple what a person heard before in speech not just repeating, but speech experience and even new to the whole language forms linguistic forms. Language speech of system units transfer, its practically real application, personal the reflection of qualities in language issues of linguocognitology,

Linguistics, sociolinguistics, pragmalinguistics and advanced science such as sociopragmalinguistics Special attention has been paid to the directions.

In front of our linguistics, "speech into language the issue of "introduction" is transverse, said O. Ducrot.

The interpretation of this issue is the current world It is extremely relevant in linguistics and is gaining importance. Perhaps Speak for 21st-century linguistics problems of practical application will remain an age of learning. So the transfer of language to speak, different in other words, issues of speech linguistics interpretation is on the agenda of our research one of the main inspection objects It is natural to organize. But this refers to the interpretation of the

language system issues, and problems at the level of the norm studied and interpreted in this field.

Of course, we do not want to say that there are no issues. It is also necessary to study this front and at the same time, it is compatible with the progress of science and should be reconsidered the issues are quite obvious.

Such issues are the phonetics of the language level, lexical-morphological, and observation on syntactic levels as well as possible for example, a sentence about syntax parts, micro, and macro systems relations, language, and speech unit's hierarchical connection, syntactic paradigmatic, functional syntax, related to semantic syntax many issues await their solution.

Statics, which depend on the dynamics of the language, is related to the rules of formation of text units. Thus, the dynamics of language became a key concept in derivation. In addition to taxonomic relations in language, there is a fundamentally different type of relations - creation relations (two derivation relations) are observed. They are the so-called dynamic system of language organization. Accordingly, applying the derivation process in two directions, i.e. semantic and formal approaches. It proves that learning by doing is possible.

As a result, it becomes possible to model derivation processes. However, the scientific interpretation of concepts such as "model", "scheme", "template", and "model" as a modeling tool is different.

Derivatology distinguishes two levels of the derivatization process with different characteristics: deep and superficial. One of the tasks of derivative derivation is to study the internal causes of processes. In addition, it is necessary to take into account that the derivation process can take place in linear and non-linear directions. When the derivation takes a linear or linear direction, a newly formed unit, a secondary language the symbol is formed as a result of changes in the structural system of the unit that is the starting point for the derivation.

In the second direction of derivation, there are no cases of expansion or contraction in the structure of the language unit without observation, only semantic changes are produced. The analysis is linear in the derivation of phrases we start by observing the cases of arrival in the direction.

It is well known that linear derivation is the direction with the most influence in the system of word combinations. Most of the units included in this system are one of their components are made based on flat fusion and this is reflected in their structural models.

For example:

	Model	Vocabulary	So`z birikmalari	Mosligi
	1.N1+N 2	stone wall	Tosh devor	+
	. N1+p	the bookof a pupil;	o`quvchining kitobi	
	r+N2	the message <u>from</u> Tashkent; a girl <u>at</u> the window; the newspaper <u>on</u> the table; a letter with the envelope	Toshkentdan xabar; deraza <u>yonida(gi)</u> qiz; stol <u>ustida(gi)</u> gazeta; xat <u>bilan</u> konvert	+
	. N's+ N	<u>grandmothers'</u> birthday; <u>boy's</u> toy	<u>buvimning</u> tugilgan kuni <u>bolaning</u> o'yinchog'i	+
	Adj+ N	white snow; rainy day	oppoq qor; yo'g'inli kun	+
	Ving +N	running dog	Chopayotgan it	+
	Ven+ pr+N	cut in pieces	bo'laklarga bo' <u>lingan</u>	+

The only difference between the models is the product of the linear derivation process presented in the table above. The formal operators of the derivation are different. The role of such operators in the above combinations of prepositions (2, 6) and „s (3) are playing the formant. Prepositions and the formant "s" characteristic of the English language in the Uzbek language assign their duties to the suffixes of agreement.

As a result, in both languages, almost the same word combinations are formed in terms of structure. Among the most active operators in English, apart from prepositions, is the zero operators (1, 4, 5), because in modern English the

adaptation of units in the syntagmatic line takes a more analytical form. This rule is not unique to the English language but also to the Uzbek language, the zero operator is a type of formal operator of derivation, as can be seen from the table (in the case of models 1 and 4).

All of the above-mentioned word combinations consist of the combination of two nominative units, and some opinions have been expressed in the scientific literature about their derivational signs. In our opinion, in the same place derivation properties of binomials remain insufficiently analyzed. Binomials, in turn, serve as a derivational basis and participate in the process of forming more extensive structural compounds can do because syntagmatic language unit possibilities are not limited to one level of valence.

List of references:

1. Ducrot O. Structuralisme: enonciation et semantique. // Poetique, 1978, No. 3, P.107-125.
2. Adlivankin S.Yu., Murzin L.N. O subject i zadachax derivatologii// Derivation i text: mejvuz. sb. Nauch. tr./Perm. Mr. flour Perm, 1984. S. 3–12. (Adlivankin S.Y., Murzin L.N. Derivatology of the subject and derivation // Derivation and text: mejvuz. sb. Nauch. tr./Perm. Mr. flour Perm, 1984. P. 3–12.).
3. Alekseeva L.M., Mishlanova S.L. Teoriya derivatsii//Vestnik Permskogo university. Vypusk No. 3(31). 2015. - S.127-135. (Alekseeva L.M., Mishlanova S.L.Teoriyaderivatsii//VestnikPermskogouniversiteta. Vypusk No. 3(31). 2015. - S.127-135.).
4. Beresneva N.I., Mishlanova S.L., Postnikova O.V. No seminary professor

